

A Cryoscopic Study of the Reaction of Ethanolamine with Aldehydes and Ketones

V. Balish and V. Ramakrishnan

The reaction of ethanolamine with some aldehydes and ketones has been studied cryoscopically.

In a previous communication¹ we reported a cryoscopic study of the behaviour of *s*-trinitrobenzene and some other organic compounds in ethanolamine. This study has been extended to the reaction of aldehydes and ketones with ethanolamine in order to obtain information concerning the electronic and steric influences on carbonyl reactivity.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used and the general procedure adopted for the freezing point determinations were essentially the same as those described in the previous paper¹. The freezing points were determined thirty minutes after preparing the solutions. Most of the aldehydes and ketones studied are readily soluble in ethanolamine. Gentle warming for about two or three minutes was found to be necessary in the case of a few compounds, but the solutions were cooled to room temperature as soon as the dissolution was complete.

p-Nitroacetophenone was prepared similarly to *o*-nitroacetophenone². Recrystallisation from acetic acid yielded a pure sample, m. p. 79-80°. *p*-Cyanoacetophenone was prepared by the method of Suzuki and Nagawa³. *p*-Methylmercaptoacetophenone and *p*-methylsulphonylacetophenone were prepared according to the method of Burton and Hu⁴. The other compounds were prepared and purified by the usual methods.

Chemical Examination of the Reaction Products

The compounds were dissolved in ethanolamine and the solutions were diluted after one hour. Acetophenone, *p*-fluoroacetophenone, *p*-chloroacetophenone, *p*-bromoacetophenone, *p*-aminoacetophenone, *p*-methylthioacetophenone, and *p*-methoxyacetophenone were recovered almost unchanged. The solution of *p*-nitroacetophenone afforded a solid on dilution. The product was immediately filtered and recrystallised from benzene. It melted at 138-39° and underwent hydrolysis when recrystallisation from 95% ethanol was attempted. (Found: C, 57.8; H, 5.9. C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₃ requires C, 57.7; H, 5.8%).

1. Balish and Ramakrishnan, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1959, **78**, 783.
2. "Organic Syntheses", 1950, **30**, 70.
3. *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1952, **72**, 305.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 601.

DISCUSSION

The reaction of an aldehyde or a ketone with ethanolamine leads to the formation of a Schiff's base (I) or an oxazolidine⁵ (II). The cryoscopic study cannot throw light on the nature of the product formed.

The *i*-factor will, however, indicate the extent to which the reaction proceeds in a given time. Since steric and polar effects are among the factors, which control the rate of a reaction, a cryoscopic study of the reaction of different carbonyl compounds with ethanolamine might be expected to provide valuable information regarding steric and polar influences on the carbonyl reactivity. The data obtained with a number of aldehydes and ketones are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Solute.	Conc. range (Molality).	<i>i</i> -Factor (observed range).
Acetone	0.24 — 0.61	1.87 — 1.92
Methyl isobutyl ketone	0.23 — 0.42	1.88 — 1.92
Cyclohexanone	0.37 — 0.44	1.84 — 1.87
Dibenzyl ketone	0.18 — 0.29	1.32 — 1.35
Benzylideneacetone	0.34 — 0.60	1.93 — 1.95
Di-isopropyl ketone	0.22 — 0.37	1.04 — 1.05
Acetophenone	0.42 — 0.53	1.02 — 1.04
Benzophenone*	0.19 — 0.34	0.98 — 1.00
<i>p</i> -Methoxyacetophenone	0.39 — 0.45	1.00 — 1.04
<i>p</i> -Methylmercaptoacetophenone*	0.09 — 0.20	0.98 — 1.03
<i>p</i> -Fluoroacetophenone	0.44 — 0.61	1.02
<i>p</i> -Chloroacetophenone	0.31 — 0.49	1.04 — 1.05
<i>p</i> -Bromoacetophenone	0.28 — 0.59	1.03 — 1.04
<i>p</i> -Aminoacetophenone*	0.29 — 0.37	0.99 — 1.01
<i>p</i> -Cyanoacetophenone*	0.24 — 0.49	1.32 — 1.34
<i>p</i> -Nitroacetophenone*	0.21 — 0.33	1.40 — 1.42
<i>p</i> -Methylsulphonylacetophenone	0.15 — 0.25	1.52 — 1.56
<i>n</i> -Butyraldehyde	0.29 — 0.54	1.89 — 1.94
Isobutyraldehyde	0.32 — 0.44	1.90 — 1.92
Chloral hydrate	0.26 — 0.44	3.00 — 3.02
Benzaldehyde	0.28 — 0.45	1.86 — 1.88
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.21 — 0.36	1.80 — 1.83
Salicylaldehyde	0.23 — 0.36	2.19 — 2.22
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde*	0.31 — 0.51	2.37 — 2.41
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde*	0.07 — 0.20	1.94 — 1.98
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde*	0.24 — 0.40	1.85 — 1.90
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.35 — 0.37	1.89 — 1.90
Anisaldehyde	0.26 — 0.40	1.91 — 1.95

*Dissolved in ethanolamine by warming slightly for about two or three minutes.

Most of the aliphatic ketones react with ethanolamine almost completely in about thirty minutes. Di-isopropyl ketone is practically unaffected. Dibenzyl ketone reacts incompletely. Steric effects seem to be responsible for the observed behaviour in these two cases. All the aromatic ketones studied with the exception of *p*-nitroacetophenone, *p*-cyanoacetophenone, and *p*-methylsulphonylacetophenone do not react to any significant extent with ethanolamine. *p*-Nitroacetophenone, *p*-cyanoacetophenone, and *p*-methylsulphonylacetophenone gave *i*-factors of 1.42, 1.33, and 1.53, respectively. Thus it is clear that acetophenone and its derivatives, containing electron-releasing substituents, do not react with ethanolamine to a measurable extent within the time allowed for the reaction. Benzophenone also does not react. Both polar and steric factors seem to contribute to the reduced reactivity of the aromatic ketones. The reactivity of a nucleophilic reagent like an amine towards the carbonyl group depends on the magnitude of the positive charge on the carbonyl carbon. The resonance structures shown below reduce the positive charge on the carbonyl carbon and make the carbonyl group less reactive. When electron-withdrawing substituents like $-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{CN}$, and $-\text{SO}_2\text{CH}_3$ are present *para* to the carbonyl group,

the positive charge on the carbon atom is enhanced and greater reactivity is conferred on the carbonyl group. It will be noted that the observed order of the reactivities of the acetophenones is $p\text{-}(\text{H}_3\text{SO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COCH}_3) > p\text{-}\text{O}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COCH}_3 > p\text{-}\text{NC}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COCH}_3$, whereas the activating influence of the substituents, as judged from their Hammett σ -constants⁶, should be in the order: $p\text{-}\text{NO}_2 > p\text{-}\text{SO}_2\text{CH}_3 > p\text{-}\text{CN}$. These orders are purely empirical and these seem to depend on several factors such as the reaction medium and the type of reaction. Unless a careful study of all these factors is made, it may not be possible to understand the theoretical basis of any relationship between the observed order of reactivities and the substituents.

The reaction of all aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes with ethanolamine went to completion within half an hour. Chloral hydrate gave an *i*-factor of three. This is due to liberation of the water molecule, involved in hydration, as the Schiff's base is formed.

The *i*-factors for salicylaldehyde and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde were 2.25 and 2.51 respectively. These values suggest that the reaction of ethanolamine with the aldehyde group is complete and the additional factors of 0.25 and 0.51 are due to the phenolic hydroxyl. Phenol itself gave an *i*-factor of 1.13 substantiating the above view. This value for phenol can be explained on the assumption that the ion-pair resulting from the interaction of phenol and ethanolamine dissociates only partially in ethanolamine.

A thorough study of the behaviour of phenols and carboxylic acids in ethanolamine will be described in a separate communication.

The authors wish to thank the Government of India for awarding a research scholarship to one of them (V. R.).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY,
ANNAMALAINAGAR.

Received February 5, 1962.